

design with 4 replications of 3 spacings (10- × 10-cm, 15- × 10-cm, and 20- × 10-m) and 3 basal N rates: recommended dose, 50 kg N/ha; 25% more N, 62.5 kg N/ha; and 50% more N, 75 kg N/ha. All treatments were topdressed with urea at 50 kg N/ha in 2 splits at 15-d intervals.

Soil was clay loam with pH 7.5, low available N, and medium P and K.

Planting aged seedlings at close spacing did not significantly increase yield. Basal application of 75 kg N/ha gave significantly higher yield. Interactions between spacing and N application rates were

significant. At 10- × 10-cm spacing, there was no significant yield difference between N application rates, but at 15- × 10-cm and 20- × 10-cm, yield increased significantly with more N. The 20- × 10-cm spacing and basal 75 kg N/ha gave the highest yield (see table). □

Stubble management for summer lowland rice

G. S. Thangamuthu, Agronomy Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore 641012, India

We evaluated stubble management to reduce the required fertilizer application for lowland rice in Jan-Feb 1982-84 at TNAU. Co 43 was planted the first season and IR20 the second. The soil was a clay loam with pH 8.0-8.5 (1:2.5 soil water ratio). Temperature varied from 17°C to 30°C during the cropping season.

N content of the stubble was 0.4-0.5% by weight. Stubbles of different heights were left in the field after harvest and plow-incorporated, then 22 kg P as powdered rock phosphate and 42 kg K as muriate of potash were applied. One week to 10 d after stubble incorporation,

Effect of stubble incorporation on N application and grain yield, Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Summer 1982-83	Summer 1983-84
Recommended dose (100-22-42 kg NPK/ha)	5.2	6.5
15-cm stubble + 25% N	4.3	5.1
30-cm stubble + 25% N	3.2	5.2
45-cm stubble + 25% N	4.0	5.0
15-cm stubble + 50% N	3.8	5.0
30-cm stubble + 50% N	5.0	5.2
45-cm stubble + 50% N	5.4	6.6
15-cm stubble + 75% N	4.4	5.6
30-cm stubble + 75% N	4.4	5.3
15 cm stubble + 15% N	4.1	5.8
CD	0.6	0.7

the field was plowed again, leveled, and the second rice crop planted. Results showed that with stubble incorporation chemical N application could be reduced without yield loss (see table).

In both years, 45-cm-tall stubble with 50% of the normal N fertilizer yielded highest among treatments and at par with the recommended application of 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha. □

Response of lowland rice to fertilizer application

H. S. Baddesha and M. S. Maskina, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

Often, a rice crop does not yield well even after liberal application of NPK. Next to N,

P deficiency can be a major constraint to yield. Experiments to identify reasons for low yield indicate Zn deficiency limits rice production in Punjab. S deficiency can also be a constraint.

We studied the response of rice to balanced nutrient application based on general recommendations and soil analysis

Soil characteristics of fields at experiment sites in Punjab, India.

Site	Texture	pH	E. C. (mmho/cm)	Organic carbon (%)	Available p ^a (kg/ha)	Available K ^b (kg/ha)
1	Sandy loam	8.7	0.20	0.48	7.5	465
2	Sandy loam	9.0	0.30	0.38	10.0	450
3	Sandy loam	9.0	0.30	0.33	10.0	420
4	Sandy loam	9.2	0.30	0.21	10.0	412
5	Sandy loam	8.8	0.30	0.45	12.5	262

^aDetermined in Olsen's extract (0.5 N NaHCO₃ solution: pH 8.5). ^bExtracted with neutral normal ammonium acetate solution.

Grain yield (t/ha)

Response of rice to fertilizers (mean of 5 sites).